

Interactive Learning Technologies in English Language

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Abstract

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of learning a foreign language today, as well as the value of interactive learning technologies used in the educational process. There is no need to prove the relevance of interactive learning, so this article is purely practical.

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Interactive learning consists in the fact that the learning process is organized in such a way that almost all students are involved in the process of knowledge, they have the opportunity to understand and reflect about what they know and think. The dominance of any participant in the educational process or any idea is excluded. Moreover, this happens in an atmosphere of benevolence and mutual support, which allows not only to receive new knowledge, but also develops cognitive activity itself, transfers it to higher forms of cooperation and cooperation. In the course of interactive training (that is, it involves interactive training), students learn to think critically, solve complex problems based on the analysis of circumstances and relevant information, weigh alternative opinions, make thoughtful decisions, participate in discussions, and communicate with other people [1, p.48].

Interactive learning simultaneously solves several tasks:

- develops communication skills and skills, helps to establish emotional contacts between students;
- solves the information problem, as it provides the students with the necessary information, without which it is impossible to implement joint activities;
- develops general teaching skills and skills (analysis, synthesis, goal setting, etc.), that is, provides the solution of educational and developmental problems;
- provides the solution of educational tasks, since it trains and teaches to work in a team, to listen to someone else's opinion [2, p.52].

Interactive learning partly addresses another significant challenge. We are talking about relaxation, relieving the nervous load, switching attention, changing forms of activity, etc. In this sense, interactive learning as a form of educational process is really able to optimize the essence, content and structure of pedagogical interactions.

By interactive learning technology (ILT), we mean a system of ways of organizing the interaction of a teacher and students in the form of educational games, guaranteeing pedagogically effective cognitive communication, as a result of which conditions are created for students to experience a situation of success in educational activities and mutual enrichment of their motivational, intellectual, emotional and other spheres. It is important to skillfully direct the teacher to achieve the set educational goals [3, p.38].

In this he will be helped by knowledge of the structure of the training process using ILT.

1. Orientation. Stage of preparation of game participants and experts. The teacher offers a mode of work, develops together with schoolchildren the main goals and tasks of the lesson, formulates the educational problem. Then it gives a characteristic of imitation and game rules, an overview of the overall course of the game and issues packages of materials.

2. Preparation for the conduct. This is the stage of studying the situation, instructions, settings and other materials. The teacher sets out the script, dwells on game tasks, rules, roles, game procedures, scoring rules (the game scoreboard is compiled). Students collect additional information, consult with the teacher, discuss among themselves the content and process of the game.

3. Play the game. This stage includes the actual process of the game. Since the start of the game, no one has the right to intervene and change its course. Only the host can adjust the actions of the participants if they deviate from the main goal of the game. The teacher, starting the game, should not needlessly take part in it. Its tasks are to monitor game actions, results, scoring, explain ambiguities and assist participants in their work at the request.

4. Game discussion. Stage of analysis, discussion and evaluation of game results. The teacher conducts a discussion during which experts speak, participants exchange views,

defend their positions and decisions, draw conclusions, share impressions, talk about the difficulties that arose during the game, ideas that came to mind.

Let's take a closer look at some of the interactive learning technologies I've used extensively in my lessons. In general, speaking of interactive learning, the concept of age restrictions, in my opinion, is absent. For example, the technology of working in pairs or triples, both permanent and rotary (replaceable). It is no secret that such technology allows you to successfully work out many aspects when teaching a foreign language.

Group work is also not new and is well known to everyone. Often in my lessons I use rotating small groups. "Country studies. Great Britain, "for more than a year I have been practicing the following scheme [4, p.58]:

Stage 1 - ahead task, collecting information on a certain plan about one of the four parts of the United Kingdom (ideally work with a multiple of four students, I had 12). The part is selected by drawing lots.

Stage 2 - work in small groups Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, England. The guys share the found information, systematize it.

Stage 3 - Small Group Work United Kingdom. Each student communicates information about their part to the entire team of the group.

Stage 4 - compare the completed tables, supplement the material, exchange views, prepare mini-stories about the United Kingdom.

The use of the Brownian Movement technology involves the movement of students throughout the class in order to collect information on the proposed topic. I often use the themes "Hobby," "Family," "Clothes," "House," while working out all kinds of grammatical constructions. Each participant receives a list of questions-tasks: "Find out how many people in your class love mint ice cream!" or "Who is dressed in a pink T-shirt today?," "Who has a desk at the window?" The teacher helps to formulate questions and answers, ensures that the interaction is conducted in English.

Sometimes we use such a form of interaction as "Borrow a position." Some statement is read out, and students should approach the poster with the word "YES" or "NO." It is desirable that they explain their position. As a logical continuation, you can use team work.

When using the Solution Tree technology, the class is divided into 3 or 4 groups with the same number of students. Each group discusses the issue and makes entries on their "tree" (a large sheet of paper), then the groups change places and add their ideas to the trees of their neighbors, without criticizing or correcting the existing ones on the sheet. You can change groups in a circle, you can stop at a certain number of "advisers." [4, p.13] The host group is redesigning additions, proposing its final solution on this issue, conducting a discussion, which sometimes develops into a debate between the parties (especially when discussing some controversial or controversial issues). The decision tree can be used by discussing the pros (one group) and cons (second group) of a question.

The Carousel technology, like many interactive technologies, is borrowed from psychological trainings. Children usually like this type of work very much. Two rings are formed: internal and external. The inner ring is immobile students facing the outer circle, and the outer ring is students moving in a circle every 30 seconds. Thus, they manage to talk a few topics in a few minutes and try to convince the interlocutor of their correctness [5, p.45]. Dialogues of an etiquette nature, the topics of "acquaintance," "nationality," "conversation in a public place," etc. are perfectly worked out. The guys talk enthusiastically, the lesson takes place dynamically and efficiently.

Similar technology "Group Story" is used by me quite often, especially when working out Past Simple and Past Continuous. Each student adds one sentence to an already started story. By a certain signal (in a minute), a sheet with an unfinished story is transmitted further in a circle. Stories turn out to be unexpected and funny.

The list of used and quite usable technologies can be continued indefinitely - these are debates, discussions, seminars and, of course, games.

There are a huge number of forms of role-playing games in English lessons: presentations, interest clubs, interviews, correspondence trips, round tables, press conferences, excursions, fairy tales, reports, etc.

For example, as part of the study of the topic "Law and Order" (grades 10-11), we always play a court hearing, and the study of the topic "Art" smoothly flows into a correspondence tour of one of the famous museums in our country.

The study of the topic "Journey" has grown into presentations by travel companies advertising different types of recreation. A group of trainees represented independent experts who decided during the discussion which advertising project was most vividly presented, winning and correct.

As part of the study of the topic "Money," we traditionally hold a round table with the goal of "finding a sponsor." The group of sponsors listens to the arguments of candidates in need of material support (roles are distributed in advance: a student who needs a scholarship; an immigrant seeking a means of learning the language; a single mother wants to give a good education to her son, etc.), asks questions, creates a situation of rivalry and manages material means. The task of each participant is to prove that he is worthy of a grant.

We gave just a few examples of the use of interactive technologies in learning a foreign language. We hope they have a place in your class. I would like to emphasize once again that these technologies allow not only to successfully solve the problems of training a teacher of a university, but also significantly intensify this process and become a condition for improving the quality of education.

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